

This document forms section nine of the University of Bath's Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

9. Guidance for organising, chairing, and taking part in assessment panels

Key points covered in this section:

- The importance of completing the required training and actively challenging conscious and unconscious bias.
- The role of the Chair and creating an environment where every panel member feels able to contribute and speak up about bias or unfair practice.

Unconscious bias

All panel members involved in research assessment must complete the University's mandatory [Unconscious Bias training](#), and the [Responsible Research Assessment training module](#).

It is good practice for the Chair to start the panel meeting by reminding colleagues to be mindful of bias, both conscious and unconscious. They should encourage panel members to recognise different experiences, perspectives and values equally, and to support each other and the principle of robust and fair decision-making by respectfully challenging bias whenever they observe it.

Briefing panels

Panels should be briefed ahead of time on the assessment process, understand the task and can ask questions or raise concerns. Again, it is good practice for the Chair to remind the panel members of the process, criteria, and responsible research assessment considerations at the start of any panel discussion. This helps set the tone and makes it easier for panel members to notice and speak up about any comments or behaviour that fall outside the agreed approach.

Speaking up

Every panel member should have an equal opportunity to contribute and share their assessment. Panels will often include colleagues of different levels of seniority or power dynamics so the Chair should be careful to make sure that everyone's voice is heard.

Panel members should be encouraged to speak up whenever something does not seem right – for example if bias is evident, there is a deviation from the agreed process or criteria, or if discussions become unbalanced.

The Chair can create this environment by reminding panel members at the beginning of the discussion that they are encouraged to contribute and to raise any concerns constructively.

For more information read [the full guidance](#) or visit the [RRA webpage](#).